

INNOVATIVE FINITE ELEMENT APPROACH FOR PREDICTING CRACK ONSET AND GROWTH BASED ON THE PRINCIPLE OF MINIMUM TOTAL ENERGY SUBJECTED TO A STRESS CONDITION

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Abstract In the context of Finite Fracture Mechanics (FFM), Leguillon (2002) introduced the Coupled Criterion of FFM (CCFFM), which forms the foundation of this study. According to CCFFM, both stress and incremental energy criteria are indispensable for the sudden initiation of a crack in a finite extension. Later, with the aim of addressing complex fracture problems including the onset and propagation of multiple internal cracks and interface cracks, Mantič (2014) proposed a modified version of CCFFM, known as the Principle of Minimal Total Energy under Stress Condition (PMTE-SC). This modification is particularly advantageous for a versatile computational implementation employing a load-stepping technique, addressing challenges related to the initiation and propagation of multiple cracks. The formulation of PMTE-SC allows the total energy to be expressed as a separately convex function of the fields of displacements, and damage variables defined along potentially new crack advances, facilitating the application of efficient and stable optimization techniques to minimize total energy with constraints.

To efficiently incorporate PMTE-SC into the ABAQUS Finite Element Method (FEM) code, we utilize UINTER, a subroutine managing the interaction between two surfaces. In this case, the interaction between surfaces of a potentially new crack advances is modeled using a continuous distribution of springs exhibiting linear elastic behavior. The mixed-mode constitutive law of these springs was described by Mantič et al (2015). The code calculates the change in potential energy using the incremental virtual crack closure technique (VCCT), which accurately reflects the change in potential elastic energy due to specific crack growth, viewed incrementally.

The developed method provides a novel approach to characterize crack onset and propagation based on CCFFM. It predicts instantaneous crack onset or propagation without the need for infinitesimal crack growth, allowing for the simultaneous appearance of multiple fractures. The computational algorithm, based on the PMTE-SC formulation, has been implemented using ABAQUS and Python scripts. Extensive testing confirms the validity, adaptability, and reliability of the proposed methodology. Rigorous examinations of mixed-mode crack scenarios, including the L-shaped plate, Single Edge Notched Plate (SENP) under shear, and the Double-Edge Notched Test evaluating Biaxial Tension and Shear, demonstrate the versatility of the approach. Validation against the classical CCFFM approach yields essentially identical results, paving the way for exploring more complex problems related to the initiation and growth of multiple cracks and delaminations.